

Outlook

Ethical Approval

From Psychology Tech Office <noreply.psy@plymouth.ac.uk>

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To (pg) Nayanika Chatterjee <nayanika.chatterjee@postgrad.plymouth.ac.uk>

Cc Matthew Hudson <matthew.hudson@plymouth.ac.uk>

You have been granted full ethical approval for your application

You may now begin your research project and recruit participants as required.

Please contact your supervisor directly if you have any further questions about your project.

Research Road Map: The School Technical Team have created a [Research](#) section to help with any research questions.